

INTERNET SAFETY

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ABSTRACT

Safety is fundamentally important for everyone, whether online or offline and is everyone's responsibility. Internet safety refers to how to be safe, confident, and responsible when using online technologies. Making the Internet safe for children has become a major technological challenge and a public policy issue. It is mainly taught in elementary and high schools. This paper provides a brief introduction on how individuals can keep themselves and their loved ones safe while they surf

Key Words: Internet Safety, Online safety, e-safety, Cyber Safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of Internet has grown exponentially over the last few decades. As the number of Internet users continues to increase worldwide, the safety of children using the Internet has become a major concern. Today, almost all US children have free access to the Internet through their homes, schools, or local libraries. Most of the Internet access is via mobile phones. Being on the Internet can be a good, valuable experience for children, who may use it to do online research projects, communicate with others, and play interactive games.

2. INTERNET ABUSE

Children typically are naïve regarding dangers in cyberspace, and their parents are not adequately prepared to help them. Teachers typically do not feel equipped to address the problem of cybersafety. It is therefore necessary to emphasize the importance of training teachers on issues associated with online technologies.

Risks to Internet use include Internet abuse, cyberbullying, privacy violations, and unwanted solicitation. However, claims that cyberspace is dominated by inappropriate material such as pornography, inflammatory, and racist writings are exaggerated. Education on Internet safety may prevent the downside to Internet use. Schools are basically responsible for ensuring Internet safety of young Internet users. School teachers can be asked to teach Internet safety in public schools [1]. But the majority of teachers have not received any formal training on Internet safety. Only parent control and lower degrees of unsafe online behavior of their children.

3. GUIDELINES FOR INTERNET SAFETY

Guidelines for online safety typically include three basic elements [2]: avoiding disclosure of personal information to strangers, creating standards for Internet access, and establishing open communication between children and adults to discuss both positive and negative cyber-experiences. The behaviors related to sharing the sensitive data (such as name and last name, personal pictures, mobile phone numbers, email addresses) on the Internet determine a range of risky behaviors in the cyber world.

Curriculum development is another approach to cope with Internet safety issues. A wide variety of curriculum materials is now available for parents, teachers, and children of different age levels. Children should be informed and taught concrete Internet safety skills [3].

4. CONCLUSION

The advantages that children have using the Internet greatly outweigh the risks involved. The educational and psychosocial benefits of using online technologies can far outweigh the potential disadvantages. Banning children from using social networking sites is unnecessary and would close them off useful tool for meeting their developmental and educational needs [4]. The Internet may be used without having negative effects on the user.

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